

Breaking Stereotypes: Unveiling the Growing Purchase Intention for Skincare Products Among Male Consumers in Toledo City Through the Lens of the Theory of Planned Behavior

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Abstract

This study investigates the factors that influence the purchase intention for skincare products among male consumers in Toledo City through the lens of the Theory of Planned Behavior. The study used a quantitative – correlational research design through surveys to determine how attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control factors influence men's decision making when it comes to buying skincare products. The study was conducted in Toledo City, Cebu Philippines with a total of 389 respondents, utilizing a purposive sampling technique to ensure that only individuals who meet the specific criteria, being male, ages 18 and above, residing in Toledo City, and having prior experience in purchasing and using skincare products are included. Findings revealed that Attitude related factors (perceived benefits, perceived effectiveness, brand trust) all had a significant influence on men's purchase intention with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.434$, $r = 0.302$, $r = 0.326$ respectively and with each having $p < .001$. Subjective Norms (peer influence from peers, friends, and social media and Gender Neutralism were also found to be a significant predictor of purchase intention ($r = 0.471$, $r = 0.299$) with each having $p < .001$. In contrast, Perceptions on Masculinity under Subjective Norms had no significant influence on men's purchase intention for skincare products ($r = -0.106$, $p = .038$). Lastly, Perceived Behavioral Control Factors such as self-efficacy, self-consciousness and price affordability significantly influenced men's purchasing intentions ($r = 0.416$, $r = 0.557$, $r = 0.303$). All variables collectively had a significant influence on men's intention to purchase skincare products, which in turn, significantly influence men's actual purchasing behavior. ($r = 0.536$, $p < .001$). Theoretically, this study strengthens the applicability of the Theory of Planned Behavior by demonstrating how attitude-related, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control factors remains as a strong predictors of male skincare purchase intention, while also highlighting the declining influence of traditional masculinity norms in contemporary consumer behavior. Practically, the findings provide valuable guidance for skincare brands and marketers to focus on product benefits, effectiveness, brand trust, testimonials, affordability, and gender-neutral marketing strategies to effectively increase men's purchase intention and actual purchasing behavior.

Keywords: Skincare, purchase intention, attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, gender neutralism, perceived effectiveness, actual purchasing behavior

Introduction

The use of skincare products has long been identified as an important part of everyday lives for many individuals. The origin of skincare began with traditional, natural remedies and through time, it evolved into a more developed and complex product formulation. Historically, one of the earliest documented records of skincare practices can be traced back to ancient civilizations such as Egypt, Greece, Rome, and in some parts of Asia, where natural ingredients such as oils, honey, herbal extracts, and clay were used to protect the skin from environmental exposure and maintain a youthful appearance (Ahern, 2022; Hale Cosmeceuticals, 2023; Lam & Lam, 2024). While these early practices highlight the long-standing importance of skincare across cultures, contemporary skincare has evolved significantly, particularly with the emergence of male skincare as a distinct and rapidly growing market segment. In recent decades, skincare has shifted from being perceived as predominantly feminine to becoming an integral part of men's self-care, health maintenance, and personal presentation. This transition reflects changing social norms,

increased product innovation, and greater awareness of skin health, thereby positioning male skincare as a relevant and important area of academic and commercial inquiry

The skin care industry continues to grow as new technologies emerge and new products enter into the market place (Castillo, 2023). Historically, majority of the marketing efforts from the skincare and beauty industry have always been targeted towards women (Anje, 2024), and it continues to promote the idea that having beautiful looking skin is a women's concern. A clear example of this is the way in which skin care companies advertise their products through billboard advertisements and social media posts showcasing almost solely female models and celebrities and utilizing packaging that is designed to appeal to women (Castillo, 2023). Today, a growing number of men are now taking efforts to achieve healthy, younger-looking skin. This makes it a good time for men to assess their skincare practices and learn about the different ways of taking care of their skin (Berger, 2024). According to a recent study of more than 11,000 Americans, it was found that good-looking men are more likely to attain better job opportunities and make more money than women (Gugushvili & Bulczak, 2023). This implies that having attractive physical features is beneficial for males in their career development and advancement whether it be earning a raise, a promotion or landing a new position that may have otherwise been unattainable.

Data published by Euromonitor International reported a 6.5% increase in the 2020 global beauty and personal care market in the area of male grooming products. Additionally, 60% of men report that they use a skin care product on a daily basis (Bradley, 2024). This upward trend is anticipated to continue as more men place greater interest in grooming and personal care. Major skincare companies have launched products specifically for male consumers in response to men's growing concerns with their physical appearance, thereby changing not only the beauty industry but also how men choose to present themselves (Bradley, 2024).

In the Philippines, the skincare market is experiencing a big rise of demand for skincare products due to the growing consumer awareness for skincare and the many benefits it provides with an estimated value reaching \$2,018.6 million by 2027 (Allied Market Research, 2021), the main reasons for this are the growing urban development that we are seeing in most cities and municipalities right now, changing consumer lifestyles, rising consumer awareness when it comes to skincare practices and the rising popularity of different skincare routines adapted from Korean beauty trends from different social media influencers as well as the rising demand for products that can help in protecting their skin against uv rays like sunscreen. These are some of the main causes of this trend and it is expected that this demand will increase for many years to come (Research MarkWide, 2025).

According to GlobalData (2022), the skincare market in the Philippines is more likely to rise to Php 74.8 billion by the year 2026 as more consumers have started to join the different beauty trends especially those that are usually seen on social media. While major metropolitan areas such as Metro Manila, Cebu and Davao represent the primary markets for skincare products in the Philippines, there is also a growing demand for these types of products in smaller rural communities and provinces like Toledo. Regional demographics, socioeconomic factors and cultural norms influence the consumption habits of the region and ultimately affect the overall dynamics of the market (MarkWideResearch, 2025). Although the skincare market is experiencing growth, the lack of research into the male consumer behavior related to purchasing skincare products represents a significant void in terms of developing an understanding of the purchase intention for skincare products among male consumers from a behavioral standpoint. Research on male skincare consumers remains limited compared to that on female skincare consumers, creating a gap in the understanding of the male skincare market (Chiu et al., 2019; Ho et al., 2020). Addressing these gaps, the present study is among the first to apply the Theory of Planned Behavior to examine the factors influencing skincare purchase intention among male consumers in a regional Philippine context.

In a study conducted by Chiu et al. (2019), indicated that while male skincare usage is growing across East Asia, male consumer behavior remains highly influenced by both social pressures and gender-related expectations. Similar to this finding, Ho et al., (2020) studied the skincare behaviors of young men in Southeast Asia and identified that many male consumers view the use of skincare products as important to maintaining personal hygiene and developing confidence. Although both studies acknowledged the exploratory nature of their results, they each noted the need for additional empirical research based on established theories of behavior to help explain what influences or limits purchase intentions among men (Ho et al., 2020; Chiu et al., 2019). Historically, marketing strategies and product development

in the skincare industry have focused almost exclusively on the needs of women. Therefore, there exists a void in the research and product design areas related to men's specific requirements and motivators when it comes to skincare (Robertson & Kingsley, 2021). Souiden & Diagne (2009), also demonstrated that although interest in male grooming is rising, some men remain hesitant to buy skincare products because of their adherence to conventional notions of masculinity.

Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB; 1991) is one of the most commonly applied framework for modelling intentions for behaviour. The TPB has been applied in many contexts - especially when it comes to consumer behaviours - as it assesses three important elements: the individual's attitude towards performing the behaviour; subjective norms (the pressure of others); and the individual's perception of behavioural control (how difficult or easy they perceive the action to be). Although the TPB has been extensively used in various domains such as public health (e.g., Dean et al., 2012), environmental behaviours (Yuriev et al., 2020), and sustainable consumption (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2008), its application to male grooming behaviour is sparse. Elfi (2023) demonstrated that the TPB could offer valuable insights into the motivations for male grooming choices and the potential psychosocial barriers associated with self image, masculinity, and peer influence. However, there is limited empirical research using the TPB to understand male consumers for skincare products.

This lack of empirical research using the TPB limits our ability to understand how both internal factors (attitudes, perceptions of self) and external factors (social norms, peer group) may shape male skincare purchase behaviours. With the increasing trend of gender-neutral marketing and self-care advocacy within the beauty industry, the disconnect between emerging trends and academic research is becoming increasingly apparent. In a study conducted by Duarte et al. (2025) underlines that an increasing number of companies are employing gender-neutral branding strategies for men, with some businesses using consumer input or current marketplace trends to determine how they will develop their brand rather than empirically studying the behavior of their customers. The lack of empirical research in this area demonstrates a critical need for academic research on how men's emerging trends in beauty products reflect on their personal values and social pressures regarding their participation in skin care. Additionally, Mintel (2022) found that over 60 percent of men who are millennials worldwide use at least one skincare product weekly; however, this has increased significantly compared to previous generations. While there are multiple reasons why there has been such a large increase in the percentage of men who use skincare products weekly, academic research continues to concentrate primarily on women. As a result, developing inclusive and effective marketing campaigns that portray skincare as a universal method of self-care requires a better understanding of the behavioral drivers for men's increasing participation in the industry.

Another significant gap is the geographic distribution of previous researches. Most available research originates from Western countries or from the very urbanized, progressive Asian markets like South Korea and Japan, which have an established male grooming industries. As a consequence, smaller or developing cities such as Toledo City in the Philippines are often missing from the academic discourse. Piamonte and Gutierrez (2021) indicated that the grooming habits of Filipino male consumers from rural areas may be more conservative compared to those from larger cities, as they are influenced by culture and religion. These findings suggest that the purchasing behaviors of males can vary greatly depending upon a number of different factors, such as socioeconomic status, local norms, and the level of exposure to global beauty trends - all of which are typically overlooked in the studies on male skincare consumptions

In an article published by local news outlet, Toledo City city has experienced a substantial rise in income and is considered as one of the wealthiest component city in the Province of Cebu with a total assets amounting to PHP 4.1 billion - reflecting its sustained economic growth and increasing consumer capacity (Osmeña, 2024). The city's growing middle-class population, paired with rising purchasing power, creates a strong foundation for market research, particularly in lifestyle and personal care products. The city is experiencing ongoing infrastructure development, including new public markets, a modern bus terminal, and residential-commercial expansions. This connectivity and development make Toledo an attractive location for both businesses and consumers, encouraging the growth of retail and service-oriented sectors, including beauty and wellness industries (Sunstar Cebu, 2023)

Similarly, according to the Cities and Municipalities Competitiveness Index (CMCI) national ranking developed by the National Competitiveness Council, Toledo City's economic growth, infrastructure development, and expanding consumer base suggest a conducive environment for studying consumer behaviors, including skincare product purchases (INQUIRER.NET, 2024). The presence of shopping centers and the increasing availability of various products provide opportunities to analyze factors influencing male consumers' purchase intentions. Toledo City's robust economic growth, strategic location, infrastructure advancements, and expanding consumer market make it an ideal setting for researching the factors affecting male consumers' purchase intentions for skincare products.

Toledo City has become a hotspot for skincare and beauty-related businesses. The rise in the number of authorized resellers and distributors of skincare products both local and international brands has expanded consumer access to a wide range of skincare options. In addition, Toledo now hosts several beauty clinics, dermatology centers, and aesthetic establishments, serving both men and women. The presence of major skincare and beauty retail chains like Watsons, along with independent skincare stores and online resellers operating locally, reflects the increasing demand for skincare products in the city.

This growing presence of skincare establishments indicates not only a strong market but also an increased awareness and acceptance of skincare practices among consumers—including males (Desiderio, 2022). Most importantly, it presents a compelling research setting for studying the factors that affect male consumers' purchase intentions for skincare products. Its strong economic foundation, ongoing urban development, expanding middle class, and flourishing skincare and wellness industry provide a rich context for understanding emerging male consumer behaviors. (Osmena, 2024)

To skincare brands and marketers, this research will offer new ways of developing marketing strategies that will be successful in appealing to, and encouraging males to adopt a habit of using skincare products. In addition to offering new ways of developing marketing strategies to skincare brands and marketers, this research has relevance to several of the United Nations' 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) including SDG #3 (Good Health and Well Being) and SDG #5 (Gender Equality).

This research supports the achievement of SDG #3 through raising awareness of skincare and increasing knowledge of skincare among male consumers. A proper skincare routine is important for the maintenance of good health and well being because it helps prevent skin disease, infection, and other dermatologic conditions. By identifying the variables that influence men's purchase intentions, this research will help improve healthy skincare routines and consequently improve self-care, hygiene, and general well-being. The findings from this research will also further support the skincare industry's efforts to develop products that are both safe and effective in contributing to the healthiness of skin.

Finally, the study will also support the achievement of SDG #5 by challenging the traditional stereotype of how men and women consume skincare products. Historically, the majority of skincare products have been targeted toward women and there has been limited effort in developing and promoting skincare products that appeals to men. This research study will challenge the stereotypical views that have developed around men in the area of skincare product and further promote the idea of a gender-inclusive marketing strategy, as well as highlight the growing interest and possible challenges associated with men making a purchase decision when it comes to skincare products. Overall, this research will support the larger goal of obtaining gender equality by reducing societal expectations and constraints on men adopting the practice of taking care of themselves (i.e., self-care) and the inclusion of men in the beauty and skincare industries.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Figure 1.
Schema of the Research Framework

Over the last few years, men's increased participation in the consumption of Skincare products has made it imperative to understand the psychological and social mechanisms that drive men's purchase behavior. To do so, the current study uses the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as proposed by Ajzen (1991), as the theoretical model to identify and determine the factors that influence male consumers' intention to buy Skincare products.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) was developed to as an expansion of the Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1975). The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) considers the two main variables; Attitude and Subjective Norms, in determining the prediction of Behavioral Intention. However, TPB adds a third variable-Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC)-to allow for the consideration of situations in which an individual does not have complete control over his/her behavior. Through the incorporation of both motivation and control elements, TPB is able to provide a more inclusive explanation of Behavioral Intention than TRA. Therefore, TPB has become one of the most commonly used and empirically verified models in Consumer Behavior Research, specifically in studies concerning the intention to purchase (Ajzen, 1991; Yang et al., 2018).

Many studies in many different disciplines have utilized TPB to demonstrate the relationship between Behavioral Intentions and Actual Behaviors and have shown TPB to be highly effective in predicting actual behavior (Ngo-Thi-Ngoc, Nguyen-Viet, & Hong-Thach, 2024). In the area of Skincare and Personal Care Products, past research has effectively utilized TPB to explain Consumers' Buying Intentions (Singhal & Malik, 2018; Shimul et al., 2022). Additionally, the model has been found to be effective in predicting environmentally conscious and health-related consumer behaviors such as Green Purchasing (Qi & Ploeger, 2021). These empirical results show the appropriateness of utilizing TPB as a viable and established framework for investigating Male Consumers' Purchase Intentions in the Skincare Market. Utilizing this theory in the current study provides a valid foundation for understanding both the formation of intent and the actual purchasing behavior of Male Consumers, in particular, in the Local Context of Toledo City.

According to the Theory of Planned Behavior, Behavioral Intentions are the most direct predictors of actual behaviors and are formed through the combination of three fundamental components: Attitudes, Subjective Norms and Perceived

Behavioral Control (Ajzen, 1991). Each of these constructs plays a distinct however interrelated role in the process of consumer decision-making.

Attitude represents an individual's general positive or negative assessment of performing a specific behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). In the context of Skincare Consumption, attitude represents how Male Consumers perceive the use of Skincare products - whether they regard such products as beneficial, useful or essential in their daily lives. When individuals believe that the performance of a behavior will produce positive consequences, then they tend to hold a positive attitude towards that behavior thus enhancing their intention to perform it. Studies have consistently demonstrated that attitude is a significant factor in forming behavioral intention (Spence et al., 2018; Maksan et al., 2019). Including attitude as a variable in this study is necessary since it explains how Male Consumers form their personal evaluations of Skincare Use. These evaluations can be affected by individual beliefs, self-perception, and evolving views of what constitutes Masculinity. An understanding of Male Consumers' attitudes will help in the development of Skincare practices and will contribute to the prediction of purchase intention in the emerging male Skincare Market.

In addition to individual attitudes, other social pressures can also determine an individual's behavior. Subjective Norms represent the degree to which an individual believes that he/she is under pressure to either perform or abstain from a particular behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Social Norms are derived from the influence of significant others, including family, friends, peers, and society. Past research has provided evidence that Subjective Norms can have a considerable effect on Behavioral Intentions in many cases related to consumption (Yadav & Pathak, 2016; Qi & Ploeger, 2019). Subjective Norms are of particular importance in the study of Male Skincare Product purchases because Men can be influenced by the opinions and actions of those around them. For example, if a man receives encouragement from family members, or if his peers give him positive reinforcement about his grooming habits or if he is exposed to widespread societal acceptance of male grooming, it is possible that he will experience an increase in his intention to make purchases of Skincare products. On the contrary, if he fears being judged or socially rejected because of his involvement in male grooming, he may be discouraged from doing so.

Gender Neutralism is conceptualized in this study as a dimension of Subjective Norms. Gender Neutralism refers to the extent to which male consumers perceive skincare products as socially acceptable for use by all genders, regardless of traditional gender boundaries. This perception is often influenced by external cues such as product packaging, branding, advertising messages, and societal discourse surrounding masculinity and grooming. When skincare products are marketed using gender-neutral language, inclusive imagery, or unisex packaging, they signal broader social acceptance and reduce the perception that skincare is exclusively feminine. As such, Gender Neutralism reflects socially constructed expectations and norms regarding appropriate grooming behavior for men. Because these perceptions are shaped by societal approval and the anticipated judgments of others, Gender Neutralism aligns conceptually with Subjective Norms within the TPB framework. A higher level of perceived gender neutrality may reduce social stigma and increase social approval, thereby strengthening male consumers' intention to purchase skincare products. By studying Subjective Norms, researchers can gain an improved understanding of whether Male Consumers receive encouragement or discouragement in the purchasing of Skincare products from those in their social networks.

The third element of TPB, Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC), is defined as an individual's belief in their own ability to perform a particular behavior, considering all the internal and external limitations (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2005). PBC describes the degree to which individuals perceive themselves to be competent, empowered, and in control of a behavior. Within the context of Skincare Usage, PBC could comprise factors such as product knowledge, financial ability, availability of Skincare products, and the confidence to use them correctly. The incorporation of PBC into this study is critical to identifying potential barriers that could inhibit Male Consumers from transforming their intended purchases into actual purchases of Skincare products. Such barriers could be internal (e.g., lack of knowledge, low self-confidence) or external (e.g., limited availability of products, unaffordable prices). Self-Consciousness is positioned in this study as a component of Perceived Behavioral Control. Self-Consciousness refers to an individual's heightened awareness of oneself as a social object and the concern about how one is perceived by others, particularly in situations that may attract social evaluation or judgment. In the context of male skincare consumption, self-consciousness may manifest as discomfort, embarrassment, or anxiety about purchasing or using

skincare products due to fear of negative evaluation, ridicule, or challenges to traditional masculine norms. These feelings can function as internal psychological barriers that limit an individual's perceived control over engaging in skincare-related behaviors. When male consumers experience high levels of self-consciousness, they may feel less confident and less capable of performing the behavior, even if they hold favorable attitudes or perceive social acceptance. Therefore, Self-Consciousness directly influences perceived control over behavior and is appropriately situated under the PBC construct within the TPB framework.

The study will determine whether Male Consumers believe that they have the required skills, resources, and opportunities to engage in Skincare activities. The Theory of Planned Behavior provides a broad-based framework to analyze the multifaceted elements that influence Male Consumers' purchase intention to purchase Skincare products. The present study utilizes this framework to analyze the way in which individual beliefs, social influences and perceived control influence purchase intention and ultimately translate that intention into actual purchasing behavior of Male Consumers in Toledo City. Ultimately, the utilization of TPB in this study not only contributes to the understanding of Male Consumer Behavior, but also provides valuable information regarding the way in which evolving social norms and the evolution of perceptions of masculinity impact Men's willingness to utilize Skincare products.

Literature Review

Gender Stereotypes Towards Skincare

Men are generally discouraged from taking part in beauty treatments while women are socially expected to conform to established feminine ideals (Dokkania, 2023). This has led to these traditional standards limiting individuals' ability to express themselves and be unique for generations. The antiquated social standard implies that people should express themselves and behave in ways determined by gender and dictate how both men and women will act. Although traditional and outdated beauty standards still exist, men are beginning to accept that skincare and personal hygiene are important elements of daily life. A concept that has been previously viewed as being only applicable to women has begun to fade as men are increasingly using skincare products and engaging in the practice of using such products for the first time. Men's skincare has traditionally been considered as a sleeping industry, but due to increased awareness of the possible benefits of skincare and the value of using skincare products to promote healthy, skin this trend is changing (DeAcetis, 2019).

While gender-based stereotyping has always played a large role in determining skincare practice, this has been a key area of focus for some companies looking to determine the best way attract their target markets and execute successful product marketing campaigns. Products designed for men typically feature characteristics such as toughness, strength and power, while products designed for women are often associated with beauty, elegance and attractiveness. The large disparity in these characteristics highlights the extent to which the public perceives individuals based on their gender, limiting the opportunity for individuals to express themselves uniquely. On the other hand, as stated by Dokkania (2023), if consumers feel confident enough to explore and utilize various skincare trends and styles that suit their unique preferences, this could lead to the acceptance of self-expression regardless of an individual's gender.

Purchase Intention

Purchase Intention is one of the numerous areas examined within the marketing discipline. Marketing academics have expressed substantial interest in Purchase Intention over the years, primarily due to the connection between Purchase Intention and consumer purchasing behavior (Dam, 2020). Purchase Intention refers to the selection made by customers in regards to whether or not they will purchase a product (Purwanto et al., 2019). Additionally, Purchase Intention is defined as the customer's desire to purchase a product or brand; it is also referred to as the probability that customers will make repeat purchases (Martins et al., 2019). Essentially, if a customer experiences a positive outcome from a product they purchased or utilized, there is a high possibility they will repurchase the same product, and therefore purchase it in the future (Peña-García et al., 2020). Many marketers use Purchase Intention as their guide to influence their marketing segmentation strategy as well as their marketing mix, since Purchase Intention has proven

itself to be an effective predictor of consumer purchasing behavior (Peña-García et al., 2020). Factors influencing consumer Purchase Intention include, but are not limited to, how the customer perceives the product/goods; their overall shopping experience; customer service; and the level of risk involved in making a purchase (Sohn & Kim, 2020).

Attitude Towards Skincare

The factors influencing men's attitude towards skincare products was explored in a study conducted by Duarte et al., (2025) where it focuses on self-care and personal grooming, and underlines the evolving perceptions of masculinity. The result of the study has found that the main reason why men buy skincare products is mainly because it was largely influence by their growing concern about their skin and how they look. The findings also revealed that social media usage had an indirect influence in purchase intentions by showing the positive effects of skincare especially when it comes to their outward appearance even though it had no direct influence.

Sukato and Elsey (2009) highlighted the notion that male consumers attitude about using skincare products tend to have a positive impact on purchase intention.

In a study conducted by Byrne and Milestone (2023) has found that most men follow some kind of skincare routine in secrecy and they don't want other people to know that they used skincare products because the traditional idea of masculinity is not entirely gone yet. This means that even though many male consumers today who are starting to use skincare products, others who uses it still wants to remain hidden because of the fear of what people might think of them if they saw him using skincare products. To understand men's motivations and behaviors regarding the daily use of sunscreen, Robert's et al conducted a study and revealed that there are around 83% of their target male population who do not really use sunscreen everyday which is an overwhelmingly huge numbers. According to their testimonies, those that used sunscreen are aiming to look younger and to lower the risk of developing skin cancer. His study highlighted that the use of sunscreen are largely influenced by income status which means that those with high incomes were more likely the ones who use sunscreens on a daily basis.

Perceived Benefits and Effectiveness

The growing number of men who are interested in purchasing and using skincare products has proven to be an intriguing subject to be studied with among many academic and industry scholars. Today, this topic has proven to be timely and relevant where skin health practices has become a major trend with some studies cited that perceived benefits is considered as one of the motivators as to why male consumers purchase skincare products. In a study conducted by Castillo (2023) where it explored the skincare habits of Filipino men has found that personal benefits such as improved skin image, prevents skin aging, and overall skin health are among the factors that significantly influences men's actual purchasing behavior. It was also mentioned in the study of Rayi and Aras (2024) that products that have perceived value, good quality, effectiveness and offers emotional satisfaction can positively encourage men to buy skincare. This means that men will most likely to invest more for skincare especially if they know that it gives the desired outcome that they want to achieve especially if that product comes from a credible brand.

Another main factor that can lead to men's purchase intention for skincare products is perceived effectiveness. Yoon and Kim (2018) underlines that perceived product efficacy can shape trust and satisfaction towards a particular item or product which results to a stronger intent for them to purchase the same product in the future. According to Kim and Seock (2019), if men have a full understanding for a particular product especially if it shows transparency about its materials or ingredients and it is backed up by scientific study is what encourages them to purchase a particular product. Lee and Ma (2021) also confirmed that if a skincare product is proven to be dermatologically tested and it's shows good results, it further adds to the products' overall effectiveness and it eventually puts more confidence for the customers purchasing the product. Their findings shows that men are most likely to invest in a skincare product especially if it has good reviews, exceptional results and it's proven to be effective.

Brand Trust

The idea of trust has been known to be an important factor that can influence long term customer relationships (Aribtha & Salim, 2025). In the business perspective, the concept of trust comes from the idea that people tend to build trust for certain product if that product is reliable and honest in fulfilling its commitments (Rasidi & Tiarawati, 2021). According to Sholikah and Nasir (2025), brand trust occurs once the consumers feel more secure for a particular

brand and have a strong faith that a brand is trustworthy and take full accountability in meeting the expectations of the customers. Most importantly, having a strong customer trust not only make the product to become known, it also help in increasing their sales. Qualtrics (2025) also define brand trust as the stage where consumers believe that a brand can fulfill its commitments it promises. Delgado (2023) also claimed that if a consumer feel secured when they buy from a specific brand it is considered as brand trust. In addition, Shopify (2024) defined brand trust as the public evaluation on the brand or company's credibility based on the message it brings to it customers, activities and the customer experience it provides. This means that if a company are honest about its products, has transparent messaging, offers excellent customers service and prioritizes its value it brings then people will most likely trust that company or brand. As mentioned by Dam (2020), brand trust can be assessed using a number of indicators like consumers' confidence in products quality, the safety and honest it gives to its customers, the reliability and having the sense of security that the customers feel when buying products from a brand.

Brand trust has been considered as one of the factors that can influence purchase intention (Dam, 2020), this means that if a customer reminds them of a particular brand and it has been known to be trusted, there is a high chance that they will purchase those products from them. Customers who put more trust in a brand are more likely to buy their products especially if they think the brand can satisfy them and meet their expectations. This supports the study conducted by Sanny et al., (2020) wherein it was highlighted that purchase intention is positively influenced by brand trust. This means that once a customer develops a strong trust in a brand, it urges them or it makes them buy the things they offer.

Additionally, in a study conducted by (Parilla, et al (2023) revealed that if brands give more focus on meeting the needs of the customers through their product, it will result in better consumer retention and builds strong customer loyalty. It also makes the customers to buy more products from them in the future. This implies that the higher the brand trust, the more chances the customer will purchase their products. This suggest that companies should maintain a positive brand image and trust in order for them to keep their customer base (Malikahasri, 2024).

Subjective Norms

In a study conducted by McCoy et (2020) entitled "Changing Masculinities: The Role of Subjective Norms in Men's Skincare" which investigates how the changing ideas of masculinity influence men in using skincare products found that men are now becoming more open about skincare practices. This means that the concept of masculinity that we all know for many years is changing and more men are now slowly using skincare products. The study also reveals that if people or peers talk and share positive comments about the products they used, it will also lead to an increase in purchasing intentions for others who are not using it yet. It shows how consumers are easily motivated to buy something, especially if others around them are talking positively about the products, which will also encourage others to buy as well. The study concludes that in order for business to effectively and successfully reach with male customers, they would also need to align the way they brand and market their products that matches with the changing ideas of being masculine.

Generally, this study will highlight how important subjective norms are especially in predicting the customers actual buying behavior for skincare products and how can businesses tailor their strategies with their target customers especially now with the changing social ideals. Marketers should also be able to adapt their marketing strategies to keep up with the changing societal norms.

Social Influence From Peers, Family And Social Media

Another external factor that can influence a person's behavior is called social influence (Hutahaeen, 2020). Social influence refers to how other people's opinions on something will influence their behavior (Adiwibowo et al. (2020). External pressures like our significant others in life such as our friends, family and our coworkers are all closely associated with social influences. In addition to culture, family, social status and other reference groups are some of the social factors that can influence consumer buying behavior.

Social media on the other hand has become a major factor in influencing people to buy and has played a huge impact on consumers intention to buy skincare products (Chrisniyanti et al. (2022). There is a study in Indonesia conducted

in the year 2019 by Syawaluddin et al., where it explore the ways on how social media marketing as well as product quality affect customer choices in buying certain products in their country. Among the factors that are mentioned in the study, product quality has the highest influence and is followed by social media advertising. This shows that the actions, trust, preferences and the encouragement of our loved ones and the people around us all have a big impact in buying certain products.

Gender Neutralism

Male consumers tend to steer clear of products they feel are overly "girly" or "feminine", primarily to avoid damaging their image of being masculine, and therefore tend to seek out products that either appear masculine or at least neutral in terms of gender. According to Spielman et al., (2021), the use of bold lettering and confident words in advertisements tend to increase the likelihood of a consumer purchasing the product. Male consumers' intent to make a purchase were also increased by the use of gender-neutral branding. Some male consumers will not purchase products perceived to be feminine, and therefore prefer products with simple packaging, neutral colors and strong messages, making these products more attractive to them. Additionally, in Westerlund's (2020) study, he stated that men tend to stay away from skincare products because they believe it is a product intended for women. Other than the type of product, and the labels on the product, the packaging of the product has an additional important function of determining the product. A single aspect that determines whether a product is for a male or a female is the label associated with the product, i.e. "for males." (Elfie, 2023) In another study conducted by McNeill and Douglas (2011), the researchers determined that other than the labels on products, one of the ways that designers can determine the gender of a product is through the colors used. The research indicated that the colors white, pink and green are generally considered to be feminine colors, while the colors blue, black and grey are generally considered to be masculine colors. Therefore, even if a skincare product has a label indicating it is for men, males would choose products with colors blue and black in its packaging, which may be perceived as more masculine than pink. (Elfie, 2023)

Products that are designed to be open to all genders and focus on the skin type rather than the traditional gender identity of a person are referred to as gender neutral skincare. Gender neutral skincare provides assurance to everyone that regardless of gender, they can purchase skincare products that meet their needs and requirements without feeling guilty or left out. Historically, gender stereotypes have been present in the manner in which people perceive skincare products, and the perception that softness is only for women and roughness is only for men, has limited self expression and reinforced the outdated and traditional gender roles (Thakar, 2024). If, however, brands focus on the functionality of the product through its ingredients and design the packaging in a gender-neutral manner for all to use, the opportunity exists to eliminate the old myths and promote self-expression and individuality by viewing skincare as a fundamental necessity, as well as provide customers with opportunities to purchase items that are consistent with their interests and needs.

Research conducted by Westerlund (2020), explored the potential influence of having a gender-neutral branding on the male purchase intention of skincare products, and the findings suggested that when male consumers purchase skincare products, they do not consider gender norms as a factor when making a decision. As an alternative, the researcher found that one of the factors that attract male consumers to purchase skincare products, including those who may attempt to avoid doing so, is the use of gender-neutral packaging designs that can be identified through the colors used. As long as the product has a simple packaging and has a good message behind it, the product will appeal to the consumer. This is especially true among younger generations, who place importance on the idea of inclusiveness, and are less likely to adhere to traditional gender norms when purchasing skincare products. On the other hand, some consumers are searching for products that offer specific features that meet their gender identity. (Aaker, 1997; Belk, 1998) Furthermore, according to Machado et al., (2021) dark color schemes, such as those found on cars and buildings, create feelings of masculinity and bright pink colors create feminine feelings.

Perception Towards Masculinity

In a study conducted by Lima (2019) reveals that most men associate beauty and skincare products that promotes the idea of masculinity while the same study conducted by Duarte et al (2025) contradicts this idea and suggests that men who think highly about the idea being masculine are the ones who are less likely to purchase skincare products. This show a potential challenge on the purchase intention of men towards skincare products due to the traditional perception

of masculinity and would make male customers feel discouraged from using skincare products due to the outdated idea that it is only a female activity (Martin and Smeeckaert, 2022).

According to Juli (2019), physical appearance plays a big influence on the way people interact with each other and how much attention they would get. It's no surprise why having a good physical appearance has been considered as an asset when it comes to social interactions, which makes people even more concerned on their looks. Kestenbaum, (2022) believes that men use skincare products to improve their looks especially among younger generations. Having a good appearance can sometimes become an advantage, especially when it comes to professional careers. Man's desire to become more youthful, having healthy skin and become good looking are some of the main reasons why we see a rise in the demand for skincare products Markley (2022).

In a study conducted by Byrne et al (2018 revealed that some men would tend to hide their skincare practices from others and it's not very common for men to walk inside the store and buy skincare products alone. Instead, they would rather let their mother, wife or their female loved ones to buy it for them (Elfie, 2023). Most men use skincare products for their faces but there are some who are not very comfortable in telling others, which leads in them buying and using skincare products in secret (Byrne & Milestone, 2022). Additionally, there are some men who maintains the traditional idea of masculinity especially with the rise of online shopping wherein people have the option to shop privately and become anonymous if they don't want other people to know the items that they bought.

According to Greenberg (2024), most brands are focusing more in developing marketing strategies that are inclusive and can effectively appeal with the highly diverse male customers. One the main drivers behind the rise of men's skincare adoption is the shift in the cultural attitudes towards the idea of masculinity and self-care (Barren, 2024). This shift is also heavily influenced due of the rise of social media where many beauty and skincare influencers are now proudly sharing their routines and pushes for a better skincare practice. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram and TikTok have also made it much easier for men to explore skincare without any shame as more men are now increasingly becoming more and more conscious of their looks and their physical appearance (Hamshaw & Gavin, 2021).

Perceived Behavioral Control

Perceived Behavioral Control as defined by Ghazali et al. (2018), refers to the ability that a person believe he or she has in order to perform a particular behavior. People with a high level of perceived behavioral control have been proven to be linked to having a higher purchase intention. Based on the study conducted by Hsu et al (2018), PBC is known to have a significant impact on consumers intention to buy green skincare products. This means that customers are more likely to buy these products when they feel that they have more authority or control of their purchasing decisions especially if they have enough financial capability to buy that certain product.

The two important components of PBC are product availability and budget limitations. For many years, research has shown us that income status and product accessibility tend to hinders people's control over their purchase decisions. For instance, Ruslim et al (2022), found that even though attitudes and strong environmental concern had a positive impact on consumers intention to buy organic skincare products, it is also important to consider if people can afford to buy those product or it's its readily available in the market. All those factors can act as barrier every time people will buy something.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy as defined by Cherry (2024) pertains to the belief in one's ability to accomplish a task or reach a target objective. This includes having enough self-assurance that they can effectively and successfully carry out their objectives. Bandura (1982) also defines self-efficacy as the belief in a person's own capability to execute all actions needed in order to accomplish what needs to do. In short self-efficacy can be associated with the person's confidence that they can succeed and perform effectively in any given situation. These ideas influence how people think, feel and act. In the case of skincare products, men with a high self-efficacy are more likely feels confident in their ability to choose and use skincare according to their will which can ultimately lead to high intention to purchase.

Li et al (2018) also highlighted that self-efficacy can significantly influenced purchase intention and suggests that customers are more likely to make a purchase if they believe that they have more control in buying it. Armitage and Conner (2001) also believe that self-efficacy is not only a valuable addition in understanding consumers intention to purchase a product but it also turns out to be the most significant predictor of consumers actual buying behavior.

Self-Consciousness

In a study conducted by Zakaria et al. (2021), it was found that some men buy skincare products only because they want to look good and feel more confident. It's no surprise that when a person feels that their skin looks healthy, they tend to feel more comfortable and feels more confident especially when facing other people in school, work, or social events. This shows how self-consciousness affects their decision to buy skincare.

According to Zaichkowsky (2020), men who are known to be highly self-conscious especially in public worries about how other people might think of them based on how they look and the way they style themselves. In a similar study conducted by Kumar et al (2024) suggest that a person's self-image serves as a mirror on how they view and describe themselves. This means that people who have a high level of mindfulness about themselves and how they interact with other people are considered to be a self-conscious individual. The same study conducted by Kumar et al (2024) also shows that there is a very strong relationship between self-consciousness and consumers purchase intention. With some studies showing that using skincare products can bring a significant impact of an individual's self-confidence about their appearance (Zhang, Adique Sarkar, Shenai Sampath, Lai & Farag, 2020) and this was driven by their strong desire to meet the social beauty standards especially in todays world where being beautiful is considered as a privilege.

Price Affordability

A consumer's purchase intention can be strongly influenced by price, especially in industries like skincare where pricing strategies are linked based on the perceived value and quality of a particular product. This means that customers are more likely to build confidence to buy a product once they believe that the prices are reasonable and its price reflects the quality of the product itself. There are some cases where it can also decrease a customer's satisfaction if they believe that the price is unreasonable and it does not reflect the quality and the value it gives to the customers. This is aligned with the study conducted by Ricardo (2021), which states that price perception refers to a customer's assessment on whether or not the price being set by the seller and the price of its competitors is reasonable, practicable, or worth purchasing. They would also be more likely to make a purchase and want to buy the same item again if they believe the pricing is fair and the product is beneficial and worth it.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the factors influencing the purchase intention of skincare products among male consumers in Toledo City using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). This paper seeks to provide insights into male consumer behavior towards skincare products and offer practical recommendations for skincare businesses.

Specifically, this study aims to:

1. Determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, marital status, occupation, educational attainment, frequency of using skincare products, how long they have been using skincare products and the type of skincare products they actively use.
2. Determine how attitude-related factors (perceived effectiveness; perceived benefits, and brand perception and trust) influence men's purchase intention towards skincare products.
3. Determine how subjective norms (influence from peers, family, and social media; gender neutralism; and perceptions on masculinity) influence men's willingness to purchase skincare products.
4. Understand how perceived behavioral control factors (self-efficacy, self-consciousness, and price affordability) influence men's likelihood of purchasing skincare products.
5. Identify key findings that can help skincare brands and marketers develop more effective strategies to target and appeal to male consumers.

Statement of Null Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Perceived Effectiveness and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between Perceived Benefits and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between Brand Trust and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products

Ho4: There is no significant relationship between Social Influence from Peers, family and Social Media and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products

Ho5: There is no significant relationship between Gender Neutralism and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products.

Ho6: There is no significant relationship between Perceptions on Masculinity and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products.

Ho7: There is no significant relationship between Self Efficacy and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products.

Ho8: There is no significant relationship between Self Consciousness and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products.

Ho9: There is no significant relationship between Price Affordability and men's Purchase Intention for skincare products.

Ho10: There is no significant relationship between Purchase Intention and men's Actual Purchasing Behavior for skincare products.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a quantitative - correlational research design to fulfill its objectives in examining the factors influencing men's purchase intention for skincare products in Toledo City using the Extended Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). Quantitative method were chosen for this study as it allows the researchers to collect and statistically analyze numerical data to identify patterns and relationship between the variables. The correlational aspect of the design was necessary to understand the degree and direction of the relationships between the variables (attitudes toward purchasing; subjective norms, and PBC); and their effect on men's purchase intention and actual buying behavior.

Research Environment

The study is conducted in Toledo City, Cebu Philippines, a first class component city located in the Province of Cebu that is known for its industrial, mining and commercial activities. As of 2020, Toledo City has approximately 207,314 residents who are exposed to modern consumer trends including skincare products. With expanding economic opportunities and evolving lifestyles, male consumers in Toledo City are increasingly receptive to self-care and grooming products. This makes Toledo City an ideal setting to examine the evolving behaviors of consumers and specifically to study how changing cultural and social norms influence men's skincare purchase intentions.

Research Participants

The participants of the study are the male consumers of skincare products who are 18 years and above and have prior experience in purchasing and using skincare products. The inclusion of only male consumers aged 18 and above is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, people within this age bracket have greater independence in making purchasing decisions compared to minors who may continue to depend on their parents financially and for decision-making on personal care products. Secondly, adult consumers are more likely to have established their own preferences, habits and views towards skincare and therefore would be better suited for evaluating the level of their purchase intention. Lastly, this age range encompasses a wide variety of male consumers from young adults who are highly influenced by social media and peer trends to older men who may prioritize skincare due to health and anti-aging concerns. The exclusion of respondents under 18 years of age limits the study as minors may lack purchasing power and therefore independent consumer behavior. Consequently, the results obtained through the survey cannot be relied upon as representative of the behaviors of men who regularly consume skincare products. Therefore, the focus of the study on

individuals aged 18 and older ensures that the data collected are reflective of the purchasing behaviors and motivations of men who actively participate in the skincare market.

Sampling Method

A purposeful sampling method was employed to ensure that all respondents selected for the study fit certain requirements namely male, aged 18 and above, resident of Toledo City, and have prior experience of purchasing and using skincare products. The researchers used this type of sampling method as it allowed for the collection of targeted data from respondents who have direct and relevant experience to the research question. In contrast to random sampling which may include respondents without previous experience in skincare consumption, purposeful sampling ensures that every respondent has firsthand knowledge of purchasing behaviors of skincare products. This contributes to the validity of the study and guarantees that the responses collected are directly relevant to the research objectives. However, it is important to note that by focusing exclusively on current users, the study may not capture the perspectives or barriers faced by men who do not use skincare products, and the findings may not fully generalize to the broader male population.

Research Instrument

The researcher used an online survey questionnaire adapted from previous studies and make necessary modification to ensure that the questions are relevant and appropriate for this study. A total of three parts, consisting of structured questions are included in the questionnaire. Part 1 provides demographic information of the respondent in terms of age, marital status, occupation and education. Questions in Part 2 ask respondents to provide general information on their usage of skincare products, including frequency and type of products purchased or used. Part 3 contains the main section of the questionnaire where respondents' attitudes, perceptions and opinions regarding the usage of skincare products are assessed. The survey questions are based on prior studies completed by Castillo (2023), Sanne & Weise (2018), Zakaria et al (2021), Charoenpoel (2016), Hall et al (2020), Sun & Wang (2020), Lee et al (2015), Huong et al (2024), Shaw (2024), Felix (2024), Westerlund (2024) and Leung, et al. (2002). The measurements of the respondent's answers are provided via a 5-point Likert Scale. The response options include: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree. The 5-point Likert Scale is widely utilized across various fields of study to provide a quantifiable representation of an individual's attitudes and perceptions.

A pilot test was performed on 30 respondents prior to the distribution of the final version of the research instrument. The objective of the pilot testing was to evaluate the internal consistency of the items within the research instrument. Utilizing the SPSS software, a Cronbach's Alpha of .823 was obtained from the analysis. As a result, a high degree of reliability was established. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient values for each of the variables of the research instrument are as follows: For items related to customers' attitudes toward the products, the Cronbach Alpha coefficients were .857 for Perceived Benefits, .925 for Perceived Effectiveness and .823 for Brand Trusts. The Cronbach Alpha coefficients for items related to subjective norms were .822 for Social Influence from Peers, Friends and social media, .825 for Perceptions toward Masculinity and .790 for Gender Neutralism. The Cronbach Alpha coefficients for items related to perceived behavioral control were .792 for Self-Efficacy, .833 for Self-Consciousness and .830 for Price Affordability. Lastly, the Cronbach Alpha coefficients for items under the dependent variable of the research instrument (Purchase Intention and Actual Purchasing Behavior) were .863 and .840 respectively. Overall, the Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the entire research instrument was .823 which means that the internal consistency is excellent.

To further substantiate the research instrument's validity, the questionnaire was also subjected to a content validation process by experts within the field. The experts reviewed the questionnaire to evaluate the suitability, clarity, and applicability of each item in regards to achieving the research goals. Some minor revisions were made to the questionnaire as a direct result of the feedback from the experts to further support the validity of the research instrument; and to ensure that it would collect the intended data. Overall, the combination of pilot testing, reliability testing, and expert validation has shown that the research instrument is both reliable and valid; and therefore, will allow for the collection of meaningful and accurate data for the study.

Data Collection

Prior to collecting data, researchers take several critical steps to ensure the feasibility of the study, ethical integrity of the study and overall value of the study. Researchers first present their original idea of the research to a panel of experts during the concept hearing defense. The panel of experts reviews the originality of the research, the feasibility of the research and the potential societal impact of the research. Feedback from the panel enables researchers to refine their research to ensure that it is worth pursuing.

Data Analysis

This research utilizes two statistical methods; Spearman Rho correlation and multiple regression analysis. Spearman correlation was used to evaluate the nature and magnitude of association among the independent variables (attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control) and the dependent variable (purchasing intention). The results from this analysis will allow researchers to identify whether or not an association exists between these independent variables and the likelihood of purchasing skincare products. Regression analysis was used to estimate the influence of the independent variables on actual purchasing behavior. Furthermore, this analysis will allow researchers to determine which of the independent variables has the greatest impact on the purchasing decision of males when it comes to their decision to buy skincare products. Using a multiple regression analysis, researchers will be able to develop an understanding of how purchasing intention mediates the relationship between the independent variables and actual purchasing behavior.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the results, the analysis and the interpretation of the data from the 389 respondents who participated in this research study using Google Forms. The results are divided into 3 major parts: the demographic profile of the respondents, the correlational analysis of each variable and the multiple regression analysis in order to evaluate the relationship of each predictor and how it influences men's purchase intention and actual purchasing behavior towards skincare products. The data were then presented in a tabular format in based with the questions from the statement of the problem and the statement of hypothesis.

Table 1
 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-22	227	58.4%
	23-27	82	21.1%
	28-32	42	10.8%
	33-37	30	7.7%
	38-42	4	1.0%
	43 and above	4	1.0%
	Total	389	100%
Marital Status	Single	321	82.5%
	Married	68	17.5%
	Total	389	100%
Occupation			

Student	250	64.3%
Private Employee	34	8.7%
Government Employee	22	5.7%
Self-Employed	40	10.3%
Business Owner	30	7.7%
Unemployed	12	3.1%
Others	1	.3%
Highest Educational Attainment		
Elementary	13	3.3%
High School	68	17.5%
Undergraduate/College	280	72.0%
Post Graduate	28	7.2%
Total	389	100%
How long have you been using skincare products?		
Less than 1 year	178	45.8%
1-5 years	149	38.3%
6-10 years	51	13.1%
More than 10 years	7	1.9%
Total	389	100%
How often do you follow a skincare routine?		
Daily	223	57.3%
Twice or thrice a week	82	21.1%
Weekly	35	9.0%
Occasionally	35	9.0%
Rarely	14	3.6%
Total	389	100%
Which skincare products you actively used?		
Face wash/ Cleanser	222	67%
Moisturizer	196	60%
Face Serum	173	53%
Sunscreen	288	88%
Body Lotion	99	30%
Anti-aging products	17	5%
Scrubs and Masks	24	7%

The first section of the research instrument was the demographic profile, which included questions on respondent's age, marital status, occupation, educational level, frequency of use of skincare products, and the types of skincare products that were currently being used.

Among the 389 respondents, a large proportion (58.4%) belonged to the 18-22 age range, implying that the greatest number of younger male individuals have a positive relationship with skincare products. The results suggest an intergenerational transition in the way males practice skincare and an openness to the concept of skincare from the

youth, primarily due to social media exposure, changing beauty standards, and increased recognition of self-care. The second largest age range (21.1%) was 23-27 years old, with a third (10.8%) aged between 28-32 years. As age increased, the percentage decreased. There were a relatively small amount (7.7 percent) of those aged between 33-37 years. However, there were very few (1%) aged 43 years and older. The reduced interest in skincare products by older males may be due to a lack of familiarity with, or a stigma surrounding, skincare routines.

Most respondents (82.5 %) were single; however, 17.5% were married. The implication of these findings is that single men may be concerned with how they appear physically to others, therefore motivating them to take advantage of skincare products. Additionally, since younger individuals generally represent the majority of singles, this may also be an indication that younger individuals are more accepting of modern grooming methods. From an occupational standpoint, students comprised the majority of the respondent pool at 64.3 %, indicating that individuals with an education level of college, and possibly beyond, are more likely to utilize skincare products. Younger, educated and employed men represent the largest segments of respondents (8.7% and 10.3% respectively) in relation to private employment and as self-employed individuals. The data regarding the level of education among the survey participants is also consistent with this analysis. More than three-fourths (72%) of the participants in the study reported they had completed their college education, indicating the relationship of higher levels of education to being aware of, and using, skin care products. Less than 1/30th (3.3%) of participants reported they had completed only an elementary education; nearly 1/6th (17.5%) of participants reported they had graduated from high school; and less than 1/14th (7.2%) of participants reported attaining a graduate degree.

Respondents were also surveyed concerning how long they have been utilizing skincare products. Approximately 46% (45.8%) of the respondents reported being skincare product users for under a year, indicating an increase in the number of men interested in skincare over recent years. Respondents were asked concerning their utilization of skincare regimens. More than fifty-seven percent (57.3%) of the participants stated they utilized a skincare regimen daily. About twenty-one percent (21%) of the participants stated they utilized a skincare regimen 2-3 times each week. Approximately nine percent (9%) of the participants stated they utilized a skincare regimen weekly. Nine percent (9%) of the participants stated they used a skincare product on occasion. The smallest group was six percent (3-6%) that reported using a skincare product rarely or never.

This research explored the categories of skincare products that male consumers most often utilize. Male consumers most often reported utilizing the following three types of products: sunscreen (88%); facial cleansers (67%); and moisturizers (60%). Each of these products represents a basic category of skincare product that could be associated with a preference among males for minimalist skincare regimens. Usage of face serums, body lotions, toners, anti-aging products, exfoliating scrubs and face masks was lower than fifty percent. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that while male consumers are increasingly adopting a routine of skincare products, they are concentrating upon the basic, essential products of their routine rather than extending their regimen to include a wider variety of products. Overall, the demographic information clearly demonstrates that interest in skincare is expanding, particularly in the areas of younger, educated, single males affected by current trends in skincare.

Table 2
 Descriptive Analysis

Variables	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Attitude			
Perceived Benefits	4.4981	.53562	Strongly Agree
Perceived Effectiveness	4.3869	.48369	Strongly Agree
Brand Trusts	4.3785	.51416	Strongly Agree
Subjective Norms			
Influence from Peers, Friends and Social Media	4.2616	.58509	Strongly Agree
Gender Neutralism			

	3.8631	.93390	Agree
Perceptions on Masculinity	2.9319	.84218	Neutral
Perceived Behavioral Control			
Self-Efficacy	4.1337	.64750	Agree
Self-Consciousness	4.1054	.64427	Agree
Price Affordability	3.7712	.57102	Agree
Purchase Intention	4.2853	.60539	Strongly Agree
Actual Purchasing Behavior	4.4518	.46918	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00=Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20=Agree; 2.61-3.40=Neutral; 1.81-2.60=Disagree; 1.00-1.80=Strongly Disagree

Table 2 outlines the descriptive statistics for the primary constructs of the Theory of Planned Behavior as applied to this study. Attitude related factors such as Perceived Benefits (M = 4.4981), Perceived Effectiveness (M = 4.3869), and Brand Trust (M = 4.3785) received the highest overall mean, all interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” These findings suggest that male consumers in Toledo City hold favorable beliefs about the functional benefits, utility and credibility of skincare products. Their strong agreement with statements regarding benefits and effectiveness reflects a strong recognition of skincare’s role in enhancing appearance and promoting skin health. Additionally, high levels of brand trust further implies that male consumers are selective especially when it comes to product quality and are more likely to engage with brands that have a reliable reputation. These positive attitudes towards using skincare products are indicative of a promising market environment for skincare campaigns specifically targeting male consumers.

Subjective Norms was evaluated using three factors to predict attitudes: Peer, Friend, and Social Media (Mean = 4.2616) influence; Attitudes toward Gender Neutralism (Mean = 3.8631); and Perceived masculinity (Mean = 2.9319). Subjective Norms indicate that many male consumers believe that social norms have a significant impact on their purchasing decisions regarding skincare products. Therefore, social norms are likely influential for validating the decision to use skincare products among males based on the opinions of others and the trends exhibited on social media. Furthermore, the fact that male consumers' attitudes toward Gender Neutralism are positive indicates a growing trend to accept skincare as not being a gender exclusive product. However, the neutral rating of male consumers on Perceived masculinity shows that male consumers continue to struggle with the perception that they should avoid or reject the idea of using skincare due to their perceived association with feminine behavior.

As for Perceived Behavioral Control, self-efficacy (M=4.1337), self-consciousness (M=4.1054) and price affordability (M=3.7712) were all interpreted as "Agree." The results of these items indicate that men have fairly high confidence that they can complete a routine related to skincare. In addition, men appear to be aware of how they look physically and view skincare as an extension of their overall image of themselves and see it as a means by which to enhance themselves physically. While respondents' responses regarding price affordability were somewhat less than those related to the first two items; however, the results do indicate that most respondents view skincare to be financially accessible.

Table 3

Correlation Between Attitude Related Factors (Perceived Effectiveness, Perceived Benefits and Brand Trust) and Purchase Intention

Attitude	N	Spearman Rho Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Perceived Effectiveness > Purchase Intention	389	.434**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho1
Perceived Benefits > Purchase Intention	389	.394**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho2
Brand Trust > Purchase Intention	389	.326**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho3

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 to 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result demonstrates a highly significant and very strong relationship ($r = 0.434$, $p < .001$) between Perceived Effectiveness and Purchase Intention. This means that the more male consumers in Toledo City believe a skincare product is effective; the greater will be their intent to purchase. The result indicates that perceived product effectiveness is an important motivator for male consumers to make a purchase and suggests that skincare brands should focus on emphasizing the effectiveness of their products through demonstration of actual results. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho1) regarding there being no significant relationship between perceived effectiveness and purchase intention is rejected.

The results are aligned with the study conducted by Sudaryanto et al (2022) which explores the different factors that influence purchase for skincare products in East Java, Indonesia. Findings revealed that product effectiveness is known to have a significant influence in purchase intention as demonstrated by a positive regression coefficient. This means that the idea of product effectiveness that is used by a certain skincare product will positively generate purchase intention in the minds of the consumers. Other studies also revealed that some customers tend to give more priority in buying skincare products, especially if they contain natural and organic ingredients because they believe it offers more effectiveness compared to other brands that may contain unfamiliar ingredients in its products. (Matic & Puh, 2016).

Zhang & Kim (2013) also explores consumer trust in skincare products and found that there is a strong relationship between perceived effectiveness and purchase intentions. This means that when male consumers believe that a skincare is effective, they're not only more likely to purchase the product itself but they will also be more likely to become a loyal customer for that skincare brand.

Similarly, perceived benefits and purchase intention also shows a statistically significant and moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.302$, $p < .001$). This suggest that male consumers in Toledo City who acknowledge the possible advantages of using skincare products are more likely to consider buying them. This supports the idea that if skincare companies emphasizes more on the how customers will benefit from the products they offer, it can positively influence their decision to buy their skincare products. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho2) stating no significant relationship between perceived benefits and purchase intention is rejected.

According to Chen (2022), skincare products that have consistent quality and benefits are known to be a main factor that increases the consumers intention to purchase. In the world of marketing, perceived benefits comes from how customers compare the losses such as the risk of getting poor quality products and high prices with the gains like the possible benefits and value it can give from a product our services. (Zeithaml, 1988; Flint et al., 1997; Forlani et al., 2002). It pertains to how customers make a personal judgement based on their impression of the value that they can potentially receive from a product or service. It could either be a gain such as the quality and good features with

reasonable prices of a particular product or a loss like time, effort and the possible risk of being unsatisfied of the product or service Zeithaml, 1988; Flint et al., 1997; Forlani et al., 2002). In the context of skincare products, the concept of perceived benefits includes improved over all skin health and having visible results which included reduces wrinkles and acnes, and the perceived loss involved such as havinh potential skin irritation due to the ingredients or having high prices that doesn't reflect the quality it provides. If the customers feel that the benefits of the products is much more higher as compare to the loss, chances are they will likely view the product more positively and if these benefits are being communicate effectively by skincare brands, it can encourage male consumers to buy skincare. This means that the stronger the perceived benefits of a skincare product, the more likely it will form a higher purchase intention especially for potential buyers of skincare.

On the other hand, brand trust and purchase intention also shows a significant and moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.326$, $p < .001$), this means that a high level of trust being put by the male customers in Toledo City for a skincare brand increases the possibility of them to purchase it. The concept of brand trust is built through consistent quality, having a good brand reputation and transparency. The findings of this study only means that skincare brand should establish a high trust and credibility of their products if they want their customers especially men to keep buying from them. Thus, our null hypothesis (Ho3) stating no significant relationship between brand trust and purchase intention is rejected.

The results are aligned with the study conducted by (Cuong 2022) which measures the role of brand trust as a bridge in the relationship between brand satisfaction and purchase intention. In his study, he defines brand trust as the customers confidence in the quality and the trustworthiness of a product or service. He also reveals that brand trust is known to have a significant and positive influence on purchase intention and suggest that skincare brands should give more focus on creating strategies that can enhance the customers level of trust which can be shown through improved customer satisfaction which can lead to purchase intention. According to Lau & Lee (1999), the idea of brand trust can be considered as the customers' strong willingness to believe in a particular brand even when faced with a lot of risk and the high expectation to deliver a good outcome. Similar study conducted by Benhardy et al (2020) supports this idea and reveals that customers feel more secure and at ease when they buy from brands that they know are very much trusted by everyone. Most importantly, when a customer feels satisfied and happy after they buy a certain product, it can further encourage them to buy from that brand again and if brands fail to live in the customer's expectation and fails to deliver what it promises to their customers, it can result in them to avoid purchasing from that brand (Swastha & Irawan, 2006). Male customers especially younger ones are also more likely to be influenced by reviews and endorsements especially if it comes from a celebrity that they idolized which can make them think that the product is trustworthy because their idols are using it (Ebrahim et al, 2016).

In the context of skincare products, brand trust plays a crucial role in shaping mens purchase intention for skincare products especially now that some men may still be relatively new to skincare and want to seek assurance to make sure that what they buy is worth it. This means that when a brand is known to be very reliable, transparent and always deliver high quality and safe products, men will more likely to feel a sense of confidence that the product will meet their needs and will not cause them any harm or any form of disappointment. Having a strong trust from a certain product or brand comes from having a positive past experience with the product, having a strong brand reputation, endorsement from experts and having an honest reviews from the different customers. For men who might still be unsure of what products to choose, having a strong brand trust increases the chances of them to try and buy products from that brand. Ultimately, the more a trust person puts in a skincare brand the stronger their intention to buy products from that particular brand.

Overall, among the three attitude-related factors, perceived effectiveness has shown to have the strongest influence on purchase intention for skincare products among male consumers in Toledo City. This means that when male consumers believe that a skincare product will work and its proven to be effective, they are more likely to plan on purchasing them. On the other hand, if men feels confident that the product will deliver what it promises, this will motivate male customers to make a purchase.

Table 4

Correlation Between Subjective Norms (Social Influence, Gender Neutralism and Perceptions of Masculinity) and Purchase Intention

Subjective Norms	N	Spearman Rho Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Influence from Friends, Peers, and Social Media > Purchase Intention	389	.471**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho4
Gender Neutralism > Purchase Intention	389	.299**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho5
Perceptions on Masculinity > Purchase Intention	389	-.106**	.038	Significant	Rejected Ho6

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 to 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 demonstrates a significant and strong positive correlation ($r = 0.471$, $p < .001$) between Influence from Peers, Friends, and Social Media and Purchase Intention. This provides empirical evidence of the significant impact of social norms on how men make decisions regarding their use of skin care. Data indicates that the attitudes and behaviors of their peers, combined with their exposure to skin care-related messages via social media, have a significant potential to influence their grooming habits. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho4) indicating there would be no statistical relationship between social influence from friends, peers and social media and purchase intention is rejected. These findings support the study of Chiou et al. (2012) who found that peer communications via social media increase product involvement and purchase conformity. Similarly, Zeng et al. (2023) indicated that peer interactions on social media can affect purchase intention through persuasive efforts and information exchange. Additionally, Sharkasi and Rezakhah (2023) demonstrated that parasocial relationships with influencers can increase purchase intention. The findings of this research are consistent with Cialdini's (1984, 2001) social proof theory in that individuals generally follow others' preferences especially when making a decision under uncertainty.

The findings of this research also support the study of Razak et al. (2021) that found social influence to be one of the major factors contributing to the purchase intention of Gen Y consumers towards local cosmetic products in Malaysia. Similar findings were reported in the studies of Shane et al (2010) and Shamsudin et al (2020) that suggest that consumers' purchase intentions are influenced significantly by their social circle and social media platforms. Furthermore, Ajzen (2011) demonstrated that social influence is a significant determinant of behavioral intentions and is viewed as one of the dimensions that relate directly to consumers' purchasing intentions for skin care products. In short, social influence from friends, peers and social media has a substantial influence on men's purchase intentions toward skin care products. Specifically, when men observe individuals that they trust such as their close friends or peers using skin care products and talking favorably about them, men are more likely to seriously consider purchasing similar products. The social validation that men receive from observing trusted individuals using skin care products reduces their hesitation to try new products and creates confidence to attempt to use skin care products. Social media

also amplifies this phenomenon by providing constant promotion of skin care through the activities of influencers, tutorials and reviews of products. Men find it much easier to learn about products through social media and thus become motivated to purchase the products due to seeing real results and relatable experiences online. Seeing these results and experiences online can generate a sense of curiosity and desire in men, thus enhancing their intent to purchase.

On the other hand, Gender Neutralism was shown to have a significant but relatively small positive correlation ($r = 0.299$, $p < .001$) between Gender Neutralism and Purchase Intention. While the strength is relatively low, the findings do suggest that acceptance of skin care as a gender neutral activity may increase the likelihood of making a purchase. The findings also highlight the need for breaking down traditional gender norms and creating inclusive branding in skin care marketing. In conclusion, since there is evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_05) which states that there is no statistically significant relationship between Gender Neutralism and purchase intentions.

The results of this study also are in line with Hämäläinen's (2019) finding which indicated that use of gender-neutral advertising and packaging could challenge traditional gender expectations and create more inclusive environments for all customers. Additionally, Lu (2019) found that a positive relationship existed between consumer gender identification and their perceived attitude and purchase intention towards a product based on the gender expression of an advertisement. Another study published in 2024 from IJISRT also shows that an inclusive marketing strategy has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of the customer. Now, products in the skin care industry are being marketed to all types of individuals.. Overall, because of the growing use of "gender-neutral," men will be able to see skin care as something normal and good for themselves and therefore more likely to purchase products that meet their needs.

Products that are marketed as "gender-neutral" are primarily focused on skin-related issues such as dryness, acne, and aging as opposed to what type of person uses the product. Therefore, products will appeal to men as they tend to want simple and effective solutions versus products that are heavily associated with a particular gender. If a man believes that a product is going to meet his needs, and that it isn't just marketed to women, he will be more likely to trust the product and ultimately make a purchase. Overall, gender-neutral products help eliminate obstacles that limit men's use of Skincare products, and ultimately, increase their intention to purchase.

Moreover, Perceptions on Masculinity and Purchase Intention show a statistically significant but weak negative correlation ($r = -0.106$, $p = .038$). In essence, men who hold to traditional views of masculinity are less likely to buy Skincare products. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_06) stating that there is no relationship between Perceptions on Masculinity and purchase intention is rejected.

This finding confirms past research on Skincare Marketing, particularly the studies by Silva & Carvalho (2024) about masculine norms. The study by Silva & Carvalho (2024) indicated that masculinity norms such as "being tough" and "independent," which were identified as reasons why males do not purchase Skincare, are changing. According to a recent post by MajCafe (2023), young city-dwelling males are now beginning to break free from those traditional masculine stereotypes and embracing Skincare routines.

Skincare/Grooming has historically been seen as part of a female identity by societal standards, so many males avoid purchasing and using Skincare products because they feel it would make them appear less masculine than if they did use Skincare products.. Internal and external barriers formed by societal expectations may deter some males from investing in Skincare products despite knowing they would benefit from the use of Skincare products. As a consequence, many males will only invest in Skincare products if those products are marketed in ways that adhere to traditional masculine value statements; i.e., strength, simplicity and functionality.

Traditional masculinity, characterized by toughness, independence, and avoidance of behaviors deemed feminine, has historically discouraged men from engaging in skincare. However, the weak strength of this relationship suggests that these norms are gradually weakening as modern masculinity increasingly embraces self-care, wellness, and grooming as compatible with male identity. Younger and urban male consumers, in particular, are challenging conventional

stereotypes and incorporating skincare into their routines, reflecting a cultural shift in which self-care and appearance management are no longer perceived as threats to masculinity. This transitional dynamic explains why perceptions of masculinity continue to influence purchase intention but to a lesser extent than in the past.

As society continues to define masculinity through the lens of self-care, emotional openness and wellness, males will begin to be more open-minded to the possibility of purchasing Skincare products. There are examples of successful Brands who have successfully redefined Skincare as part of a healthy and confident male lifestyle instead of just a beauty routine. The advertising of Skincare products that utilize male role models, athletes, and/or influencers that portray Skincare usage as normalizing Skincare usage can lead to positive influences on attitudes and increased purchase intentions among males. The evolving views of masculinity represent one of the most influential factors to consider when determining whether males will actively resist or support the exploration and investment into Skincare based upon how well the Skincare product represents the male's self-image and social identity.

Table 5

Correlation Between Perceived Behavioral Control Factors (Self Efficacy, Self-Consciousness and Price Affordability) and Purchase Intention

Perceived Behavioral Control	N	Spearman Rho Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Self-Efficacy > Purchase Intention	389	.416**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho7
Self-Consciousness > Purchase Intention	389	.557**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho8
Price Affordability > Purchase Intention	389	.303**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho9

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 to 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 shows a significant and moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.416$, $p < .001$) between Self-Efficacy and Purchase Intention. This means that once a person has confidence in its ability to use skincare products appropriately can lead to a greater purchase intention. Hence, the null hypothesis (Ho7) stating no significant relationship between Self-Efficacy and Purchase Intention is rejected.

The results are aligned with the study conducted by Li & Xu (2019) which found that self-efficacy played an important role in the relationship between purchase intention and actual buying behavior. In the context of consumer buying behavior, self efficacy has been known to have an influence to a variety of decision making processes which includes product evaluation, information search, and purchase intention (Lee & Lee, 2018). Aside from that, individuals who have a high level self-efficacy are more confident in understanding the product attributes and making informed purchase decisions which leads to a higher chance to buy. This supports the idea of Ajzens (2002) Theory of Planned Behavior which states that self-efficacy is known to be a significant predictor of behavioral intention.

When men feel confident in their own ability to choose and use skincare products correctly, they are more likely to use and purchase skincare products. This sense of competence comes from past positive experience of the product, the knowledge about skincare routines, or information coming from advertising and product instructions. This means that men with higher self-efficacy are less likely to feel intimidated or feel embarrassed by the idea of using skincare and instead they are the ones who are more open to use and embrace skincare products.

On the other hand, men who happens to have a low self efficacy tends to avoid buying skincare products due to their fear of making the wrong choice and they view skincare as a complicated feminine habits which can creates hesitation to buy. This lack of confidence reduces their willingness to try new products or to commit to a skincare routine. This suggest that enhancing self efficacy through education, clear product labeling, and creating relatable marketing campaign can positively influence men's intentions to buy and consistently use skincare products.

On the other hand, Self-Consciousness and Purchase Intention also shows a significant and strong positive correlation of $r = 0.557$, ($p < .001$). This means that men who are more concerned about their physical appearance are more likely to purchase skincare products. It pushes the idea that having the motivation to look good are considered as important factor in why men use skincare. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_08) stating no significant relationship between Self-Consciousness and Purchase Intention is rejected.

The results are aligned with the study conducted by Ricciardelli and Williams (2012) which shows that increasing social pressure and the changing beauty standards have greatly contributed to how men become more conscious about themselves and their looks, which can lead to a higher willingness to buy skincare products.

As defined by Fenigstein, Scheier, & Buss (1975), self-consciousness refers to the level to which individuals are aware and are concerned with how they are being seen by others. In the context of consumer behavior studies, self conscious individuals focuses more on having a good appearance and are likely to be influenced by social beauty trends.

Moreover, Price Affordability and Purchase Intention also shows a significant and moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.303$, $p < .001$). This suggests that although men in Toledo City are willing to spend on skincare products, their choices still largely depends by the products perceived value and how much budget does the person. Thus, our null hypothesis (H_09) stating no significant relationship between Price Affordability and Purchase Intention is rejected.

The same study conducted by Chen et al (2022) highlighted that price is considered to be one of the primary factors that can influence consumers purchase intention. Some consumers tends to evaluate on whether a certain product is worth buying or not. He also mentioned that if the price is reasonable or the product is good and worth buying, there is a higher chance that it will increase their purchase intention, and they would likely purchase the same product the next time. Additionally, the study also found that females perceptions when it comes to price are different than those males and reveals that females care more about the price and the value of a skincare product as compare to males.

Price affordability has also long been known as a crucial factor that can influence a consumer purchasing behavior. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), price is considered as one of the most highly sensitive components of the marketing mix because it directly impacts consumers' perceptions of value and their willingness to buy a product. In the context of skincare where quality and effectiveness are equally important, price still remains an influential factor, especially for customers with tight budget. In a study conducted by Zeithaml (1988), he emphasized the concept of perceived value and reveals that consumers tend to evaluate a product's worth by weighing its benefits against its cost. In the case of skincare while some users may be motivated by quality, ingredients, or brand reputation, their final decision still relies on whether the product is fairly priced for the value it offers.

On the other hand, having high prices can also create a barrier most especially if men are not yet sure about the true value of the product. Without a clear understanding of it's benefits or visible results, expensive skincare products may be seen as unnecessary spending and this is especially true for male consumers who prioritize practicality in their purchasing decisions. As a result, brands that offer quality skincare solutions at affordable prices are more likely to attract and retain male customers as this increases both the intention to purchase and the chances of turning that intention into actual buying behavior.

Overall, among the three perceived behavioral control factors, self-consciousness has the highest predictive value and was also the most influential factors among the three variables. This means that when male consumers are more aware of their appearance and how others may see them, they are more likely to buy skincare products.

Table 6
Correlation Between Purchase Intention and Actual Purchasing Behavior

	N	Spearman Rho Correlation Coefficient	Sig.(2- tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Purchase Intention > Actual Purchasing Behavior	389	.536**	<.001	Significant	Rejected Ho10

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Finally, Table 6 shows a significant and strong positive correlation ($r = 0.536$, $p < .001$) between Purchase Intention and Actual Purchasing Behavior. This means that intention is known to be a strong predictor of mens actual buying behavior for skincare products among male consumers in Toledo City. This confirms the importance of turning positive attitudes and intentions into actions through accessible and highly appealing products. Hence, our null hypothesis (Ho10) stating no significant relationship between Purchase Intention and Men's Actual Buying Behavior is rejected. It is important to note that Actual Purchasing Behavior was self-reported by respondents, reflecting their personal accounts of prior skincare purchases. This suggests that interventions and marketing strategies that successfully strengthen male purchase intention—by emphasizing product effectiveness, social endorsement, and lifestyle alignment—are likely to translate into real buying behavior.

This finding is consistent with what being proposed in the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) as well as the study of Brown (2003) who underlines that consumers with intentions to buy certain product will demonstrate a higher actual buying intention than those customers who show that they have no intention of buying.

For marketers of skincare products, this finding suggests that promoting customers intention to buy skincare products is very important because this will lead them to buy the products itself. For men, having a strong purchase intention toward skincare often involves a mix of personal and basic needs, social influence of the people around them, the people they look up to and the changing attitudes toward skincare. This means that when men perceive skincare as something that is highly beneficial to them, accepted by our society, and it fits to their lifestyle, their intention to purchase will most likely increases especially when the product is supported by positive reviews or comments and shows effective and visible results from using the products itself.

Table 7
Influence of Attitude Related Factors (Perceived Benefits, Perceived Effectiveness and Brand Trust) on Men's Purchase Intention.

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	Coefficients	Coefficients	Beta			
Constant	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Attitude						
PB	.163	.062	.144	2.618	.009	Significant

PE	.329	.071	.263	4.638	<.001	Significant
BT	.164	.065	.139	2.522	.012	Significant

Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

p-value: <.001

R-Squared: .745

Interpretation: Significant

Table 7 presents the results of the multiple regression analysis assessing the impact of attitude-related factors namely Perceived Benefits (PB), Perceived Effectiveness (PE), and Brand Trust (BT) on men's purchase intention towards skincare products. The three predictors were all statistically significant at with P Values less than 0.05, demonstrating a positive relationship between Attitude Related Variables and Male Consumers Purchase Intention with an R-squared value of .745 showing that 74.5 percent of the variation in Male Consumers Purchase Intention was explained by the Attitude Related Factors. Perceived Effectiveness (PE) showed the greatest positive relationship toward Male Consumers Purchase Intention with a Beta Coefficient of .263 and T-Value of 4.638; Men will consider purchasing Skincare Products if they believe the product will be Effective. Perceived Benefits (PB) demonstrated the next most significant relationship with a Beta Coefficient of .144 and T = 2.618; This indicates that Men have begun to realize the Personal Benefits associated with Skincare Use. Brand Trust (BT) demonstrated the least significant but still statistically significant relationship toward Male Consumers Purchase Intention with a Beta Coefficient of .139 and T = 2.522; Thus, Brand Credibility appears to enhance Male Consumers Purchase Intentions toward Skincare Products.

The above findings support research completed by Boon (2020). The purpose of this study was to identify the factors that affect the purchase intent toward Natural Skincare Products among Gen Y Consumers in Malaysia. The study demonstrates a significant relationship between Attitude and Purchase Intent toward Natural Skincare Products among Gen Y Consumers.

It also supports the findings of Kim & Chung (2011) and Sukato & Elsey (2009), which underlines that there is a strong relationship between attitudes towards natural skincare products and their willingness to buy and it is primarily motivated by their desire to improve their appearance. This was further validated through the findings of Vazifehdousta et al. (2013) which reveals that positive attitude towards skincare products defines the consumers willingness to purchase among Malaysian university students. Previous study conducted by Mamun et al. (2024) which investigates the factors that motivates Bangladeshi consumers to purchase skincare products and found that there is a significant positive relationship between consumer attitudes and their intention to buy skincare products. Similarly, according to Verbecke & Vackier (2005), if a customer has a positive attitude towards a certain product, he or she is more likely to buy, while negative attitude reduces its tendency in purchasing that particular products. On the other hand, it contradicts the study conducted by Seavmey & Piriypada (2023) which explores the factors that influence the purchase intention for Thai skincare brands among Cambodian Customers and revealed that attitude have no significant impact on the purchase intentions among Cambodian Consumers for Thai skincare brands. As defined by Ajzen (1991), when consumers exhibits a good attitude towards a certain behavior, their behavioral intention also increases.

Results indicate a change in perspective for male consumers in Toledo City, which represents a move away from traditional masculine views. Marketers and skincare companies should focus their messaging around the product's effectiveness and trustworthiness since these male consumers are now associating skincare products with their effectiveness, benefit and reliability of the product or company. Campaigns should include real-life testimonials and scientific data to help create perceived value and perceived effectiveness of the product. The campaigns should also be a part of an ongoing branding campaign to increase long term brand trust with this developing segment of male consumers.

To summarize, all three of the attitudinal variables significantly impacted the men's intentions to purchase skincare products. Perceived Effectiveness (PE) had the greatest effect (.310 Beta, $t=4.46$, $p<.01$) followed by Perceived Benefits (PB)(.194 Beta, $t=3.20$, $p=.02$) and finally Brand Trust (BT)(.148 Beta, $t=2.38$, $p=.02$). It appears that the male consumer will have a greater propensity to create an intention to purchase if he perceives the product as being effective, providing him some benefit to his health, and coming from a reputable source. The finding from the research supports past studies, such as those conducted by Castillo (2023), where she investigated the relationship between attitudes toward purchasing skincare products and services among Filipino consumers and it was found that attitudes contribute positively to Purchase Intention.

Table 8

Influence of Subjective Norms (Influence from peers, family, and social media; Gender neutralism; and Perceptions on Masculinity) on Men's Purchase Intention.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		
Constant						
Subjective Norms						
IPFS	.458	.050	.443	9.191	<.001	Significant
GN	.067	.031	.104	2.153	.032	Significant
PM	-.017	.032	-.024	-.539	.590	NS

Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

p-value: <.001

R-squared: .623

Interpretation: Significant

A regression analysis was conducted to assess the influence of Subjective norms (Influence from peers, family, and social media; Gender neutralism; and Perceptions on Masculinity) on men's purchase intention towards skincare products. Table 15 presents the result of the regression analysis on Subjective Norms as predictor variable of men's Purchase Intention towards skincare products, with an R-squared value of .623 indicating that the predictors can explain 62.3% of the variation in purchase intention.

Among the sub-variables tested, Influence from Peers, Family, and Social Media (IPFS) showed a significant and positive impact (Beta = .443, $t = 9.191$, $p < .001$), indicating that external social influence strongly affects men's intentions to buy skincare products. On the other hand, Gender Neutralism (GN) were also found to be a significant predictor of purchase intention (Beta = .104, $t = 2.153$, $p < .032$). Lastly, Perceptions on Masculinity (PM) were found to be not significant ($p = .560$) with Beta value close to zero (Beta= -.024).

The results supports the findings of Jun (2020) which investigates the purchase intention for green skincare products among college students in Malaysia. The study reveals that social norms has a significant relationship on the purchase intention among Malaysian university students. This is further validated by Lee (2009), which considered social influence to be the key predictors of the purchasing intention among young consumers. Similarly, according to the findings of Joshi & Rahman (2016), social influence tends to have the highest predictive power when it comes to understanding the factors that motivates consumers to purchase skincare products.

On the other hand, the result contradicts the findings of Seavmey & Piriypada (2023) which reveals that on the case of Cambodian consumers, subjective norms was found to have no significant influence on purchase intention for skincare products. In a study conducted by Boon et al. (2020) which explores the factors the influence the purchase

intention towards natural skincare products also reveals that subjective norms have no significant relationship on purchase intention. Similarly, the same study conducted by Mamun et al. (2024) which investigates the purchase intention and buying behavior for skincare products among Bangladeshi consumers. The study reveals that the influence of subjective norms on purchase intentions have no significant effect. This suggests that social pressure or influence from friends, peers and social media do not significantly affects Bangladeshi consumers towards buying skincare products. Instead, their intention to buy skincare products are primarily motivated by personal beliefs. This correlational divergence may be explained by cultural differences, as Filipino society is characterized by strong collectivist values and the principle of *pakikisama*, which emphasizes social harmony, group cohesion, and maintaining good relationships with peers and family. In such a context, the attitudes and behaviors of close social networks, including friends, family, and trusted influencers, can play a powerful role in shaping individual intentions, making social endorsement a key driver of male skincare adoption.

This finding suggests that while societal norms and expectations may generally discourage male skincare use, the direct influence of personal and social networks appears to override those broader cultural expectations. The results imply that in Toledo City, men are more likely to develop purchase intentions when skincare use is normalized or encouraged by people they trust such as friends, family, and influencers. On the other hand, it contradicts the study conducted by Chiu et al. (2019), which investigates the factors that influence young Chinese men to purchase skincare products and found that reference group such as friends and family does not have an emotional or psychological connection that drives young men to purchase skincare products.

Perceptions on masculinity were found to have no statistical influence on the purchase intent of men towards skincare products. This indicates that masculinity perceptions may not contribute to the purchase intent of men toward skincare products. It has been commonly assumed that contemporary male consumer purchasing decisions can be attributed to one of two factors; changing (evolving) gender norms and/or being bound by traditional masculine ideals. The data does not support these assumptions. The lack of statistical significance supports that men may not consider whether a skincare product is promoted via gender neutral branding, nor are they likely to be motivated by the relationship between using the products, and their adherence to traditional views of masculinity or non-traditional views of masculinity. Instead, men may be making purchase decisions based upon preference, quality, effectiveness and lifestyle choices versus ideology. This finding challenges most marketing assumptions and suggests that utilizing marketing strategies which aim to redefine masculinity and/or promote inclusivity via gender neutral branding will likely result in very little changes in men's actual purchasing behaviors within the male skincare industry.

The above findings also emphasize the value of using peer influence and social media advocacy in marketing efforts, particularly through the use of male influencers/role models/public figures that are seen as trustworthy, and who openly use skincare products.

Table 9

Influence of Perceived Behavioral Control factors (Self-efficacy, Self-consciousness, and Price affordability) on Men's Purchase Intention.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t		
Perceived Behavioral Control						
SE	.202	.049	.216	4.083	<.001	Significant
SC	.208	.054	.221	3.861	<.001	Significant

PA	.176	.056	.166	3.125	.002	Significant
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Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

p-value: <.001

R-squared: .798

Interpretation: Significant

Table 9 illustrates how the three independent variables, namely Price Affordability (PA), Self Efficacy (SE), and Self Consciousness (SC) influence the purchasing intentions of males. The R-2 for this regression model is .798, which indicates that 79.8% of the variance of the dependent variable (purchase intention) is explained by the three independent variables. All three variables have been identified as statistically significant predictors (all $p < .001$ for SC and SE; $p = .002$ for PA) of men's purchase intention for Skincare Products. In addition, Self-Consciousness (SC) had the largest standardized coefficient (Beta = .221) while Self-Efficacy (Beta = .216) had the next largest and thus both variables appear to have a major impact on men's decision to make a purchase related to Skincare products. While price affordability was also a significant predictor, its Beta Coefficient (.166) was significantly smaller than that of self-consciousness and self-efficacy, indicating that while it may have some influence, it appears to be a much less influential factor compared to self-consciousness and self-efficacy.

The results is aligned with the study conducted by Seavmey & Piriypada (2023) which investigates the factors that influence the purchase intention among Cambodian consumers for Thai skincare brands. The study reveals that perceived behavioral control had a positive impact on purchase intention. This means that when the product attributes matches their capability, they tent to have a more positive outlook when it comes to making purchases. Similar study is conducted by Syifaa (2020) which investigates the purchase intention of green skincare products among college students in Malaysia . The results of the study also reveals that perceived behavioral control had a significant and positive impact on purchase intention for skincare products among Malaysian university students. This is also confirmed by a study conducted by Alam & Sayuti (2011), which evaluates the intention to purchase product related to food and reveals that perceived behavioral control had a significant relationship on purchase intention. On the other hand, the result contradicts the findings of Boon et al. (2020) which explores the purchase intention towards natural skincare products among Gen Y consumers in Malaysia . The study reveals that there is no significant relationship between perceived behavioral control and purchase intention for natural skincare products. The findings oppose those of Kim & Chung (2011) who found that the greater the perceived control of purchasing and belief that one could purchase, the higher will be the intention to purchase among consumers.

Men's purchase intent toward skincare products is influenced by their self-efficacy and self-consciousness, as well as other perceived behavioral control (PBC) factors. Men's perception of their capability to make skincare decisions and the extent to which they are self- conscious about their appearance or personal hygiene influences their intent to purchase; the greater the sense of self-efficacy, the greater the sense of self-consciousness, the greater the purchase intent. This implications are evident: Skincare marketing must be designed to empower men through framing it as an easy-to-use product that will improve their appearance while being cost-effective. Promotional efforts may address these behavioral controls through tutorial advertising, user-friendly packaging, and value bundles of products that represent a good value to the consumer.

In general, all of the variables for Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC) were statistically significant predictors of men's purchase intentions. A desire to look better (self-consciousness) was the greatest predictor of men's purchase intentions (beta = .238, $t = 3.708$, $p < .001$). Men will also be more likely to purchase skincare products if they perceive themselves as having the appropriate psychological ability to adequately care for their skin (self-efficacy) (beta = .222, $t = 3.756$, $p < .001$), and if the products are priced in such a manner that the product(s) are affordable (price affordability) (beta = .168, $t = 2.875$, $p = .004$). Therefore, the primary driver of men's purchasing decisions is their strong desire to improve their physical appearance, and their decision to pursue a skincare product is contingent upon whether they believe they have the ability to adhere to a skincare regimen and the cost of the product.

Skincare marketers and companies need to demonstrate how easy and accessible skincare routines are - especially to first-time users; in addition, offering a range of products with varying price points will enable the widest possible audience of male consumers across different income brackets.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The results revealed that attitude related factors (perceived benefits, perceived effectiveness, brand trust) all had a significant influence on men's purchase intention, indicating that male consumers respond favorably to positive product evaluations. Subjective Norms (peer influence from peers, friends, and social media and Gender Neutrality) were also found to be a significant predictor of purchase intention, reinforcing the impact of societal acceptance in reshaping gender norms. In contrast, Perceptions on Masculinity under Subjective Norms had no significant influence on men's purchase intention for skincare products. This suggests that men's decisions to purchase skincare are likely driven more by practical concerns such as product effectiveness, personal grooming needs, or brand reputation rather than ideological or identity-related factors like adherence to traditional masculine norms. Lastly, Perceived Behavioural Control Factors such as self-efficacy, self-consciousness and price affordability significantly influenced purchasing intentions, highlighting the role of self confidence, price value and appearance awareness as key predictors in their willingness to purchase skincare products. Generally, all constructs collectively had a significant influence on men's intention to purchase skincare products, which in turn, significantly influence actual purchasing behavior. These findings support the framework of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), demonstrating that attitudes, social influences, and perceived control shape the intent and actions of male consumers in the skincare market.

One of the major findings of this study is that out of the many different variables tested, the three strongest predictors of purchase intent were perceived benefits, brand trust and self-consciousness. Therefore, men are primarily driven to purchase skincare when they believe that the product will produce effective and desirable results, when they trust the brand as a reliable and trustworthy source, and when they feel extremely confident in their ability to utilize the product effectively. One of the key findings indicate that self-consciousness, or the desire to improve one's physical appearance, as one of the strongest predictor of men's purchase intentions for skincare products suggesting that men are primarily motivated to engage in skincare when they feel aware of or concerned about their looks, highlighting the central role of appearance-related concerns in driving behavior. While self-efficacy and price affordability also significantly influence purchase intentions, the stronger effect of self-consciousness indicates that personal appearance is the most salient factor compelling men to act. Essentially, men are more likely to purchase skincare products when they perceive that using them will enhance their physical presentation, reflecting the psychological influence of self-image on decision-making and the critical importance of addressing appearance-related motivations in marketing and product design. Additionally, the results also indicated that purchase intent is a statistically significant predictor of actual purchase behavior indicating that the individuals intentions will serve as a guide to make decisions to purchase skincare products.

The results of this research study have also demonstrated that peer influence significantly contribute to male consumers acceptance of the concept of utilizing skincare products. When male consumers see that the utilization of skincare products is accepted and utilized by their social circle and peers in their daily lives, then these same male consumers will be more likely to accept and utilize the products themselves. Another significant findings of this research study was the demonstration of the influence of gender neutrality with regards to male consumer preferences. Based on the results, most of the male consumers in Toledo City do not necessarily care whether the skincare product was labeled as being for men or for women as long as the product produced favorable results. This highlights the changes taking place within society today and that skincare is no longer viewed as a product that is exclusively designed for women but rather is a common practice that most people engage in their everyday lives.

The paper serves as a critical validation of the Theory of Planned Behavior, as it demonstrates the translation of intention into real action. In the context of Toledo City's skincare market, it signifies that once men develop the intent

to purchase skincare products driven by attitude, subjective norms, and behavioral control, they are likely to follow through with an actual purchase. This bridges the gap between psychological readiness and consumer behavior, emphasizing the importance of nurturing purchase intentions through strategic campaigns. For skincare brands, this means that converting awareness into intention is not a wasted effort, it directly drives sales.

To conclude, findings of this study revealed that most male consumers in Toledo City are becoming progressively more open in using skincare products and are actively moving beyond the antiquated century-old societal norms that view skincare as something that should only be used by females. The results of this study demonstrated that purchase intent for male consumers can be heavily influenced by their own individual perspectives such as identifying the functional benefits and advantages of using skincare products and the influence of social groups including friends, family members and other loved ones. In addition to having a high degree of self-efficacy will increase the confidence of males to utilize skincare products and will allow them to feel empowered enough to purchase the products. Most importantly, the results of this research study have confirmed the practical application of the Theory of Planned Behavior developed by Ajzen (1991) in the context of understanding the factors that will influence male consumers desire to purchase skincare products. Specifically, the results of this research study have demonstrated that the attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioral control of male consumers will collectively contribute to the decision-making process of male consumers when considering the purchase of skincare products. The results of the research study indicate that the majority of male consumers in Toledo City are beginning to break free from the long-standing stereotypical perceptions of men and are beginning to show a greater acceptance of utilizing skincare products; particularly when the products provide effective and measurable results, come from reputable and trustworthy brands, and are user-friendly and manageable for male consumers to use. The results of this research study will not only present new marketing opportunities for skincare brands and marketers but will also create a positive cultural movement that will enable men to begin viewing skincare as an essential component of their overall health, hygiene and wellness.

Recommendations

Based on the results and findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed that can be used for future research in the field of marketing and consumer behavior.

For Skincare Brands

In order to develop and market male skincare products that meet the demands of the increasing number of men interested in skincare, brands should focus on developing and promoting male skincare products that emphasize practicality, such as skin protection, acne prevention, hydration and wellness; rather than simply emphasizing aesthetic appeal. Brand messaging should also be based on the functional aspects of the product and its transparency and the product's performance should be clearly demonstrated through credible data and transparent labeling. Additionally, brands should refrain from reinforcing traditional or outdated views on what is perceived as masculine/feminine when it comes to beauty/grooming, and focus on promoting a universal concept of "skincare" as a normal part of one's overall personal grooming routine (regardless of sex) and therefore appealing to a growing number of men who are becoming more interested in using skincare products. Brands should also recognize the importance of creating products that appeal to a broad spectrum of men, regardless of income level. Given that price affordability is a significant factor influencing men's purchase intentions, particularly in regional settings such as Toledo City, local brands are encouraged to introduce sachet-style packaging or smaller product sizes to reduce financial risk and lower entry barriers for first-time users. Offering products across a range of price points—including affordable trial options—can increase accessibility for students, working adults, and lower-income consumers, thereby expanding the male skincare market and encouraging wider adoption. If skincare brands create products that come in a variety of different price ranges, they may be able to make their products affordable enough to purchase for a wider group of male customers (e.g., students, working adults, low-income individuals).

For Marketers

Marketers are encourage to develop marketing campaigns that normalizes the use of skincare products for men by showing how skincare products are a way of taking care of oneself, hygiene and empowerment. Marketers should also highlight the testimonies of male users of various skincare products to further establish social acceptance and

encourage others to follow in their footsteps. Given the strong influence of social norms and social media on male purchase intention, marketing efforts should prioritize digital platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, where skincare content is highly visible and influential. Rather than relying solely on traditional celebrities, brands should collaborate with relatable male influencers, including lifestyle content creators, fitness enthusiasts, and everyday professionals, who can authentically demonstrate skincare use as part of a normal daily routine. Additionally, marketing strategies should highlight the ease of use, simplicity and time efficiency of utilizing skincare products, specifically for male consumers. Some men are either new to skincare products or are hesitant to start using skincare products due to beliefs that its too complicated or too "Girly" for their use. Thus, marketing campaigns should promote easy to follow, step-by-step Skincare Routines specific to the needs of men and require minimal efforts to make it seems less daunting and more attainable especially for first-time users of skincare. Lastly, marketing content should be both educational and non-intimidating when explaining basic skincare routines and dispel the belief that skincare is a product exclusively for one gender only.

For Male Consumers

Male consumers are encouraged to embrace skincare as a form of self-care and seeing it not as something that we can brag about but rather as an essential component of our overall health. The study has shown to us that when men see skincare as something that beneficial for the and it socially acceptable for everyone, their intention to purchase and use such products will also likely to increase. Therefore, male consumers can benefit from becoming more informed about their individual skin needs and find products that suit their lifestyle and needs and eventually building a simple yet consistent skincare habits.

For Policymakers and Health Advocate

Policymakers and organizations focused on public health are well-positioned to support this emerging trend by incorporating skincare awareness into their public health programs -- particularly in schools and community-based wellness programs. Framing skincare as a component of preventive health and overall well-being—rather than as a cosmetic or vanity-driven practice—aligns with Sustainable Development Goal #3 (Good Health and Well-Being) and helps reduce the stigma associated with skincare use among men. Early education on basic skin protection, hygiene, and disease prevention can encourage men to adopt healthy skincare practices at a younger age. Promoting skincare as a fundamental aspect of a person's health and wellness program, and therefore reducing the stigma associated with using skincare products, and encouraging men to start using skincare products earlier. In addition, policymakers and the public health sector can work together with local brands and influencers to promote affordable and accessible skincare products in remote areas and promote greater accessibility to skincare products for all people regardless of their sex or socio-economic status.

For Future Researchers

Future researchers are encouraged to build on this study by exploring other regions, age groups, or sociocultural contexts to understand how perceptions of skincare vary across different male demographics or perhaps they can also explore studies that look into the possible barriers that prevent male consumers from purchasing skincare products. Future studies should also include male non-users of skincare products to explore the psychological, social, and structural barriers that prevent them from engaging in skincare products. Additionally, future researchers may also include qualitative methods such as interviews to capture a much deeper insights into the motivations and barriers male consumers face in purchasing skincare products, providing a more comprehensive insights into both adoption and resistance behaviors - thereby contributing to a more holistic understanding of male skincare consumption.

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